

Explicit formulas for the Jordan normal forms and matrix exponentials of 2×2 matrices

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Abstract

We present an explicit formula of the Jordan normal forms of 2×2 matrices and give explicit formulas of 2×2 matrix exponentials. While the general theory is abstract, we will demonstrate that the entire theory can be completed using only the four basic arithmetic operations in the case of 2×2 matrices.

Keywords: 2×2 matrix, Jordan normal form, matrix exponential

Jordan normal form is an advanced topic of linear algebra. Although it would be standard practice to omit the detail of Jordan normal forms in basic linear algebra courses, it would be good to introduce examples of non-diagonalizable square matrices and their Jordan normal forms with simple calculations. See (Strang, 2023) for instance. This note provides an explicit formula to give the Jordan normal forms of 2×2 matrices and an application to computing matrix exponentials. This note is basically based on the fact that the eigenvalues of a 2×2 matrix are all either the same or different from each other. We denote the set of all complex $n \times n$ matrices by $\mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$. Let us start with the diagonalization formula of 2×2 matrices.

Theorem 1. For $A = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$, the characteristic polynomial and the discriminant are

$$\det(zE - A) = z^2 - (a + d)z + (ad - bc), \quad D = (a - d)^2 + 4bc$$

respectively, where E is the identity matrix. Suppose that $D \neq 0$. We denote by \sqrt{D} a branch of the square root of D , say, if $D = \rho e^{i\theta}$ with some $\rho > 0$ and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$, set $\sqrt{D} = \sqrt{\rho} e^{i\theta/2}$. We have the following.

- (i) If $b = 0$ and $c = 0$, then A is a diagonal matrix.
- (ii) When $b \neq 0$, if we set

$$P := \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \frac{-a + d + \sqrt{D}}{2b} & \frac{-a + d - \sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix},$$

then we have

$$\det(P) = -\frac{\sqrt{D}}{b} \neq 0, \quad P^{-1}AP = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a + d + \sqrt{D}}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a + d - \sqrt{D}}{2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

(iii) When $c \neq 0$, if we set

$$P := \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a-d+\sqrt{D}}{2c} & \frac{a-d-\sqrt{D}}{2c} \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

then we have

$$\det(P) = \frac{\sqrt{D}}{c} \neq 0, \quad P^{-1}AP = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a+d+\sqrt{D}}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a+d-\sqrt{D}}{2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Proof. (i). Suppose that $b = c = 0$. Then A becomes a diagonal matrix.

(ii). The proof of (ii) and (iii) is the standard procedure of diagonalization of square matrices whose eigenvalues are all distinct. We show (ii) and (iii) only by elementary calculation without using the theory of eigenvalues and eigenvectors explicitly. Suppose that $D = (a-d)^2 + 4bc \neq 0$ and $b \neq 0$. The following calculations are performed in the same order as the double signs. We compute

$$\begin{aligned} A \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{-a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{-a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} a + \frac{-a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2} \\ c + \frac{-ad+d^2 \pm d\sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2} \\ \frac{2bc - ad + d^2 \pm d\sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The second entry of (3) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2bc - ad + d^2 \pm d\sqrt{D}}{2b} &= \frac{4bc - 2ad + 2d^2 \pm 2d\sqrt{D}}{4b} \\ &= \frac{4bc + a^2 - a^2 - 2ad + d^2 + d^2 \pm 2d\sqrt{D}}{4b} \\ &= \frac{4bc + (a-d)^2 - a^2 + d^2 \pm 2d\sqrt{D}}{4b} \\ &= \frac{D - a^2 + d^2 \pm 2d\sqrt{D}}{4b} \\ &= \frac{(d \pm \sqrt{D})^2 - a^2}{4b} \\ &= \frac{a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2} \cdot \frac{-a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2b}. \end{aligned}$$

Substitute this into (3), we have

$$A \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{-a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{-a+d \pm \sqrt{D}}{2b} \end{bmatrix}.$$

If we set P as in (ii) of Theorem 1, we deduce that $\det(P) = b \neq 0$ and

$$AP = P \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a+d+\sqrt{D}}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a+d-\sqrt{D}}{2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Multiplying the above identity by P^{-1} from the left, we obtain (1).

(iii). Suppose that $D = (a-d)^2 + 4bc \neq 0$ and $c \neq 0$. Set

$$J := \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B := JAJ = \begin{bmatrix} d & c \\ b & a \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then $J^2 = E$, and B is in the same condition of A in Part (ii). Set

$$Q := \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \frac{a-d+\sqrt{D}}{2c} & \frac{a-d-\sqrt{D}}{2c} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$P := JQ = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a-d+\sqrt{D}}{2c} & \frac{a-d-\sqrt{D}}{2c} \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then we have

$$\det(P) = \det(J) \det(Q) = \frac{\sqrt{D}}{c} \neq 0,$$

$$JAP = BQ = Q \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a+d+\sqrt{D}}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a+d-\sqrt{D}}{2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Multiplying the above by J from the left, we have

$$AP = JQ \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a+d+\sqrt{D}}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a+d-\sqrt{D}}{2} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$= P \begin{bmatrix} \frac{a+d+\sqrt{D}}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a+d-\sqrt{D}}{2} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Multiplying the above identity by P^{-1} from the left, we obtain (2). This completes the proof. \square

In general, Theorem 1 is useless since basic linear algebra courses provide the theory of diagonalization of diagonalizable square matrices. However, this note can presents the arithmetic-based complete theory of canonical forms of all 2×2 matrices combining Theorem 1 and the the next theorem.

Theorem 2. For $A = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$, the characteristic polynomial and the discriminant are

$$\det(zE - A) = z^2 - (a + d)z + (ad - bc), \quad D = (a - d)^2 + 4bc$$

respectively. Suppose that $D = 0$. We have the following.

(i) If $b = 0$ and $c = 0$, then $A = aE$.

(ii) When $b \neq 0$, if we set

$$P := \begin{bmatrix} b & 0 \\ -(a - d)/2 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

then we have

$$\det(P) = b \neq 0, \quad P^{-1}AP = \begin{bmatrix} (a + d)/2 & 1 \\ 0 & (a + d)/2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

(iii) When $c \neq 0$, if we set

$$P := \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2 & 1 \\ c & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

then we have

$$\det(P) = -c \neq 0, \quad P^{-1}AP = \begin{bmatrix} (a + d)/2 & 1 \\ 0 & (a + d)/2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Proof. (i). Suppose that $D = (a - d)^2 + 4bc = 0$ and $b = c = 0$. Then $a = d$ and $A = aE$.

(ii). Suppose that $D = (a - d)^2 + 4bc = 0$ and $b \neq 0$. We construct an invertible matrix P so that the diagonal elements are the same and also $b \neq 0$ is used to eliminate $c = -(a - d)^2/4b$. Then we have an invertible matrix $P := \begin{bmatrix} b & 0 \\ -(a - d)/2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$ and $P^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/b & 0 \\ (a - d)/2b & 1 \end{bmatrix}$. We deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} P^{-1}AP &= P^{-1} \left\{ \frac{a + d}{2}E + \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2 & b \\ c & -(a - d)/2 \end{bmatrix} \right\} P \\ &= \frac{a + d}{2}E + \begin{bmatrix} 1/b & 0 \\ (a - d)/2b & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2 & b \\ c & -(a - d)/2 \end{bmatrix} P \\ &= \frac{a + d}{2}E + \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2b & 1 \\ \{(a - d)^2 + 4bc\}/4b & 0 \end{bmatrix} P \\ &= \frac{a + d}{2}E + \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2b & 1 \\ D/4b & 0 \end{bmatrix} P \\ &= \frac{a + d}{2}E + \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2b & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b & 0 \\ -(a - d)/2 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= \frac{a + d}{2}E + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (a + d)/2 & 1 \\ 0 & (a + d)/2 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

(iii). Suppose that $D = (a - d)^2 + 4bc = 0$ and $c \neq 0$. Set $B := JAJ$. Then $J^2 = E$, and B is in the same condition of A in Part (ii). Set

$$P := JQ = \begin{bmatrix} (a - d)/2 & 1 \\ c & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q := \begin{bmatrix} c & 0 \\ (a - d)/2 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

P is invertible and then we have

$$P^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1/c \\ 1 & -(a-d)/2c \end{bmatrix}, \quad Q^{-1}BQ = \begin{bmatrix} (d+a)/2 & 1 \\ 0 & (d+a)/2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

We deduce that

$$P^{-1}AP = Q^{-1}JAJQ = Q^{-1}BQ = \begin{bmatrix} (a+d)/2 & 1 \\ 0 & (a+d)/2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

This completes the proof. \square

The judgment of diagonalizability of square matrices and how to diagonalize diagonalizable matrices are standard topics in basic linear algebra courses, and the full theory of Jordan normal forms is often reserved for advanced courses. Theorem 2 would be useful to show non-diagonalizable square matrices and their Jordan normal forms in basic linear algebra courses. Learners can overview the theory of canonical forms of square matrices.

The matrix exponential of a square matrix is a standard topic of basic ordinary differential equation courses. This gives fundamental solutions to systems of first-order linear ordinary differential equations with constant coefficients. For any $A = [a_{ij}] \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$, the matrix exponential e^A is defined by

$$e^A := \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^k}{k!}, \quad A^0 := E.$$

Each element of the above infinite matrix series converges absolutely, and e^A is well-defined. Indeed we have

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left| (i, j)\text{-element of } \frac{A^k}{k!} \right| \leq 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{n^{k-1}a^k}{k!} \leq e^{na}, \quad a := \max_{i,j=1,\dots,n} |a_{ij}|.$$

We have by the definition a formula

$$e^{P^{-1}AP} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(P^{-1}AP)^k}{k!} = P^{-1} \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{A^k}{k!} \right) P = P^{-1}e^A P \quad (4)$$

for any invertible matrix $P \in \mathbb{C}^{n \times n}$. See (Strang, 2023) for instance. We have explicit formulas for e^{tA} ($t \in \mathbb{R}$) for $A \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$ by using (4) and the canonical forms of 2×2 square matrices.

Theorem 3. *Suppose that $A \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$. We denote its eigenvalues by λ and μ , that is, $\det(zE - A) = (z - \lambda)(z - \mu)$.*

(i) *If $\lambda \neq \mu$, then*

$$e^{tA} = \frac{e^{\lambda t}}{\lambda - \mu} (A - \mu E) + \frac{e^{\mu t}}{\mu - \lambda} (A - \lambda E). \quad (5)$$

(ii) *If $\lambda = \mu$, then*

$$e^{tA} = e^{\lambda t} E + t e^{\lambda t} (A - \lambda E). \quad (6)$$

Proof. (i). Suppose that $\lambda \neq \mu$. Theorem 1 implies that there exists an invertible matrix P such that

$$P^{-1}AP = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \mu \end{bmatrix}, \text{ and}$$

$$e^{tA} = P e^{tP^{-1}AP} P^{-1} = P \begin{bmatrix} e^{\lambda t} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{\mu t} \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} = e^{\lambda t} P \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} + e^{\mu t} P \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1}. \quad (7)$$

We have

$$P \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} = \frac{A - \mu E}{\lambda - \mu}, \quad P \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} = \frac{A - \lambda E}{\mu - \lambda}, \quad (8)$$

since

$$P^{-1}(A - \mu E)P = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda - \mu & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad P^{-1}(A - \lambda E)P = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mu - \lambda \end{bmatrix}.$$

We substitute (8) into (7) to obtain (i).

(ii). Suppose that $\lambda = \mu$. Then the discriminant of A vanishes. We apply Theorem 2 to A . When the off-diagonal elements of A are all zero, then $A = \lambda E$ and $e^{tA} = e^{\lambda t} E$. Otherwise, there exists a 2×2 invertible matrix P such that

$$P^{-1}AP = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 1 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix}, \quad e^{tA} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{k!} P \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 1 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix}^k P^{-1}. \quad (9)$$

Induction argument on k implies that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 1 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix}^k = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda^k & k\lambda^{k-1} \\ 0 & \lambda^k \end{bmatrix}, \quad k = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (10)$$

We deduce that

$$A - \lambda E = P(P^{-1}AP - \lambda E)P^{-1} = P \left(\begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 1 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix} \right) P^{-1} = P \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} \quad (11)$$

We substitute (10) and (11) into (9). We deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} e^{tA} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{k!} P \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & 1 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{bmatrix}^k P^{-1} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\lambda t)^k}{k!} P \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{t(\lambda t)^{k-1}}{(k-1)!} P \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} \\ &= e^{\lambda t} P \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} + t e^{\lambda t} P \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} P^{-1} \\ &= e^{\lambda t} E + t e^{\lambda t} (A - \lambda E). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Note that when $\lambda \neq \mu$, if we set

$$P_\lambda := \frac{A - \mu E}{\lambda - \mu}, \quad P_\mu := \frac{A - \lambda E}{\mu - \lambda},$$

then $P_\lambda + P_\mu = E$. Using this identity and the Hamilton-Cayley theorem $(A - \lambda E)(A - \mu E) = O$, we show that P_λ and P_μ are projection matrices:

$$P_\lambda P_\mu = O, \quad P_\lambda^2 = P_\lambda, \quad P_\mu^2 = P_\mu,$$

where O is the 2×2 zero matrix. Moreover (5) becomes

$$e^{tA} = e^{\mu t} E + \frac{e^{(\mu-\lambda)t} - 1}{\mu - \lambda} \cdot e^{\lambda t} (A - \mu E), \quad (\lambda \neq \mu).$$

This implies (6) provided that $\mu \rightarrow \lambda$. On the other hand, when $\lambda = \mu$, we have two cases $A = \lambda E$ and $A \neq \lambda E$. If $A = \lambda E$, then $e^{tA} = e^{\lambda t} E$ and the second term of the formula vanishes.

Solving second-order linear ordinary differential equations with constant coefficients and solving 2×2 systems of first-order ordinary differential equations with constant coefficients are central topics of basic courses on ordinary differential equations. Indeed, these equations and systems arise in classical physics such as the damped harmonic oscillator and various two-dimensional flows. So how to solve these equations and systems is important for mathematics, modeling and computational thinking, natural and social sciences, etc. The method of solving 2×2 systems develops into planar vector fields, their integral curves, and classification of orbits. In terms of the real-valued 2×2 systems, if the discriminant D of the characteristic polynomial of the matrix is negative, then the solutions are oscillatory.

The integral curve $(x(t), y(t))$, $t \in \mathbb{R}$ for a planar vector field $(ax + by, cx + dy)$, $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}$ is determined by the 2×2 system of linear ordinary differential equations of the form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} x(t) \\ y(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x(t) \\ y(t) \end{bmatrix}$$

Using Theorem 3, one can concretely derive the integral curve passing through an arbitrary point (x_0, y_0) at $t = 0$ by hand. We now show in Figure 1 two examples of planar vector fields

$$(0.5x - 1.5y, 1.2x - 0.3y), \quad (-0.1x + 1.1y, 1.1x - 0.1y),$$

and their integral curves created by the Julia Programming Language:

Figure 1. Planar vector fields and their integral curves

Theorem 3 is not necessarily useful for drawing integral curves. We actually used the Julia Programming Language to draw integral curves in Figure 1. More precisely, we used `CalculusWithJulia.jl` package to draw the vector fields and `DifferentialEquations.jl` package to solve the system of equations numerically.

While all we did in this note are elementary computation, all the description did not lose rigorosity at all. This means that one can follow all the topics in this note only by elementary computation. In particular, it provides the complete theory for matrix normalization and a complete method for matrix exponential calculation, although it is limited specifically to 2×2 matrices and systems. As a result, solving 2×2 systems of first-order linear ordinary differential equations becomes just quadrature. We will be glad if this note will be helpful for instructors and learners of basic linear algebra or ordinary differential equations.

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